

ANALYSIS OF PUNISHMENT MITIGATING CIRCUMSTANCES CHARACTERIZING A PERSON WHO COMMITTED A CRIME (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE CRIMINAL LAW OF UZBEKISTAN)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10902182>

Annotation: In this thesis, the author analyzes the circumstances that facilitate the punishment characterizing the person who committed the crime, which is taken into account when prescribing punishment, within the framework of the criminal law of Uzbekistan. In particular, the importance of a minor person and a pregnant woman as an mitigating condition for committing a crime is highlighted. The recognition of the culprit's state of pregnancy as a punishment mitigating condition is an expression of the state's concern for the protection of the health of the expectant mother and child, while the criminalization of a minor is recognized as a punishment mitigating condition criminal law is a valid expression of the humanitarian principle.

Keywords: underage person, pregnant woman, punishment mitigating condition, humane principle, psychophysiological feature.

The mitigating circumstances of the punishment characterizing the person who committed the crime, which are taken into account in the appointment of punishment, are established based on the need for separate criminal legal protection of certain categories of persons, based on their physiological and psychological peculiarities. The recognition of a minor's Commission of a crime as a mitigating condition of punishment as defined in Section 55 of the criminal law is a valid expression of the humanitarian principle of criminal law. Age-related and psychophysiological characteristics of individuals of this category are valid as a basis for the relief of punishment. The legislator takes into account that the consciousness of a teenager is at the stage of formation, and he is not able to objectively and correctly assess the situation that has arisen in certain cases. Underage individuals sometimes commit crimes under the influence of adults, in imitation of them, with the intention of placing themselves in opposition to the public interest. It is also necessary to take into account that it usually does not take a long time to morally correct a minor. It is much easier for juvenile offenders to have a corrective effect on morality, therefore, in most cases, there is no need to apply harsh penalties to them.

In the legal literature, some authors propose, as a mitigating case of punishment, to recognize not the fact that the culprit is still a minor himself, but in what way his minor influenced the person to commit a crime. For example, Serkov writes: “when imposing penalties on minors, the courts must consider this situation as an unenforceable abstraction. In each specific situation, it is necessary to approach the solution of the issue separately, based on the characteristics of the age categories of minors [1]”.

Minkowski and Tuzov note that the younger the person being prosecuted, the greater the importance of minors in the sum of the mitigating and aggravating circumstances of the sentence [2].

According to some authors, the situation under consideration when prescribing penalties for minors who have committed a serious or very serious crime cannot be considered as a mitigating condition for punishment. In particular, according to Stanovsky, although there are no norms in criminal law on the condition that the punishment be relaxed in the presence of mitigating circumstances, the court is obliged to relieve the punishment to a minor to some extent, only when there are extreme consequences of the committed crime, the court has the right to deviate from this obligation, citing irrefutable motives of its decision [3].

Scriabin writes: ‘a minor should not be allowed to refer to a defendant's minor as a mitigating condition of punishment in cases where a person is convicted of a crime for which the law provides for imprisonment for more than ten years or the death penalty [4]’.

Ignatov also attributes the consideration of the culprit's underage as a mitigating condition to the severity of the crime committed, believing that the condition could not affect the mitigation of punishment in cases where a serious crime was committed [5].

The culprit's underage cannot be counted as a mitigating condition under Section 55 of the criminal law, since it is taken into account when drawing up the sixth section of the criminal law, called “characteristics of Juvenile liability”, which, based on the humanitarian principle, sets the maximum limits of penalties assigned to minors: the maximum limits of penalties assigned to minors differ significantly from the maximum limits of In section six of the General section of the criminal law, and in the manner provided for in Section 55, the imposition of a penalty on a minor arises the repeated consideration of the same case, which violates the rule that the same case cannot be counted twice. Therefore, from Part 1 of Section 55 of the criminal law, it is necessary to

issue a mitigating condition of punishment provided for by paragraph “j”-“the commission of a minor's crime”.

Instead of this mitigating situation, we propose to include in the Criminal Law a mitigating situation regarding the presence of incapacitated citizens in the child or care of the culprit. Until this time, the fact that we have young children of the culprit has not been seen as a mitigating condition of punishment, but this situation has been taken into account by the courts both in the appointment of punishment and in the analysis of information about the identity of the culprit. In particular, paragraph 7 of the plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on the practice of prescribing punishment for a crime by courts” enshrines the following provisions: the law does not limit the scope of circumstances that mitigate punishment. For this reason, other circumstances not mentioned in this article at the time of the appointment of a sentence can also be considered as a mitigating condition (for example, the first occurrence of a crime of not great social danger, the presence of a young child of the defendant, the fact that the crime is committed due to compassion for someone, medical or other assistance to the victim after the commission of a crime directly by the culprit, and so on) [6].

Another condition is associated with a woman's pregnancy. The recognition of the culprit's pregnancy as a state of mitigation of punishment is an expression of the state's concern for the protection of the health of the expectant mother and child, as evidenced by the realization of the principle of humanism. The reasons why the commission of a crime in this case is considered a mitigating condition for punishment are the fact that the physiological changes that occur in a woman's body during pregnancy have a serious impact on her psyche [7].

In the legal literature, it is possible to face various interpretations of the content of the state of mitigating the punishment under consideration. For Example, P.P.While Serkov highlights the content of the situation that alleviates this punishment, at the same time, he points out that it is about the commission of a crime by a woman who is in a state of pregnancy. In his opinion, the crime should have taken place not before or after pregnancy, but precisely during pregnancy. If the pregnancy is caused after the commission of the crime, the court will be deprived of the possibility of easing the punishment by applying the gestational basis of the Criminal Law at the time of the appointment of punishment [8]. In our opinion, this point of view of the author is justified. M. In this regard.H.In order for Rustomboev to also be recognized as a state of

mitigation of punishment, it has a special obligation for a woman to become pregnant in the act of committing a crime [7].

At the same time, it is worth noting that in most foreign countries, the “state of pregnancy” itself, and not the “crime of a pregnant woman”, is a state of mitigation of punishment. We support this view and propose that Section 55 (1) “Z” of the criminal law is stated in the context of “pregnancy status”. In this case, it will be necessary to take into account the fact that a woman is pregnant not only at the time of the crime, but also in the period before the court verdict is issued, as a mitigating condition for the punishment. Through this, the state will take into account the interests of the child to be born, the normal development and birth of the mother in the womb, as well as the interests of the family when prescribing punishment for a pregnant woman. Already, in accordance with Article 65 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the state protection of motherhood and childhood is necessary.

In addition, we can conclude that Section 55 (1) of the criminal law states that “a person with a disability or we offer to supplement the sentence with a mitigating condition” the crime of a woman over 60 years old or a man over 65 years old”. We would already have taken into account that their age, physical and mental capabilities are limited.

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